

the corresponding non-mercurated oxazolidinones (Ia and Ib).

Bactericidal activity: The bactericidal activity of synthesised compounds, both mercurated and non-mercurated ones have been assayed against two common pathogenic bacteria, *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, separately by Rideal-Walker serial drop dilution method⁹. The results are given in Table I. Both the bacteria are equally sensitive towards the compounds Ia and Ib at 100 ppm level.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the B.S.I.R., Government of Orissa for financial assistance. One of the authors (S.C.S.) is grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a Teacher Fellowship.

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Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones as Antibacterial Agents

S. J. SHAH, S. R. SHAH, N. C. DESAI and K. A. THAKER

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002

Manuscript received 30 January 1984, accepted 26 May 1984

PHENYLACETIC acid have been known to be active as bactericidal and fungicidal agent. Thiazolidinone derivatives are well known biological active compounds¹⁻⁶. Several substituted thiazolidinones were found to possess anaesthetic, anticonvulsant and sedative properties^{7,8}. Besides, compounds having N—C—S grouping have antitubercular⁹, antiradiation¹⁰, hematocidal¹¹ and antibacterial¹² activities. In view of the varied physiological activities of thiazolidinone derivatives several thiazolidinone derivatives have been prepared (II) by the cycloaddition of thioglycolic and thiomalic acid with different hydrazones (Schiff's base).

where R' = H and
R' = -CH₂.COOH

Experimental

Phenylacetylhydrazines: These were prepared by the reported method¹³.

Hydrazones (I): A mixture of phenylacetylhydrazine and aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol each) in ethanol (30 ml) and piperidine (3-4 drops) was refluxed on water bath for 1 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, the separated solid was filtered and the product (I) recrystallised from ethanol. Melting points, yield and antibacterial activity of (I) are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - HYDRAZONES (I)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Antibacterial activity	
			<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	148	-	-
2.	-2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	187	-	+
3.	-4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	166	+	+
4.	-5.Br.2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	198	+	++
5.	-4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	197	-	-
6.	-3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	183	-	-
7.	-4.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	153	-	+
8.	-3,4-CH ₃ (O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	209	-	+
9.	-4.OH.3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	135	+	+
10.	-3,4-di(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	168	+	+
11.	-4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	204	-	-
12.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	137	-	-

C, H, N analyses within ±0.5% theoretical values. Yield 65-75%.

+ = Zone dia. <20 mm.

++ = Zone dia. >20 mm.

- = No inhibitory zone.

4-Thiazolidinone (II): Method A. A mixture of appropriate hydrazone (I) (0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.015 mol) in dry benzene (30 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. Excess solvent and thioglycolic acid was removed under vacuum. The residue was washed thoroughly with NaHCO₃ solution and water, dried, and the product (II) crystallised from ethanol (95%).

Method B. A mixture of hydrazone (I) and thiomalic acid (0.01 mol each) was condensed in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h. The temperature was raised to 180° for 30 min, and the product dissolved in sodium bicarbonate (4 N) solution and filtered. The filtrate was

TABLE 2—4-THIAZOLIDINONES (1)

Sl. no.	R	R'	M p. °C	Antibacterial activity	
				<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	H	160	-	+
2.	-2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	178	-	++
3.	-4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	175	+	+
4.	-5.Br.2.OH.C ₆ H ₃	H	218	+	++
5.	-4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	H	150	-	-
6.	-3NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	H	115	-	-
7.	-4.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	118	+	+
8.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	125	-	+
9.	-4.OH.3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	H	176	+	++
10.	3,4-CH ₂ (O).C ₆ H ₃	H	160	-	-
11.	-4OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	215	-	-
12.	-3,4-di(OCH ₃).C ₆ H ₃	H	220	+	+
13.	-C ₆ H ₅	-CH ₂ .COOH	116	+	+
14.	-2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	159	+	++
15.	-4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	104	++	++
16.	-5.Br.2OH.C ₆ H ₃	-CH ₂ .COOH	129	-	-
17.	-4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	173	-	+
18.	-3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	-CH ₂ .COOH	175	-	+
19.	-4.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	105	-	+
20.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	108	+	++
21.	-4.OH.3OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	-CH ₂ .COOH	120	-	-
22.	3,4-CH ₂ (O).C ₆ H ₃	-CH ₂ .COOH	177	+	+
23.	-4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	115	-	-
24.	-3,4-di(OCH ₃).C ₆ H ₃	-CH ₂ .COOH	110	+	++

C, H, N analyses were within $\pm 0.5\%$ theoretical values. Yield 55-60%.
Other notations same as in Table 1.

reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid and the product (II) crystallised from ethanol (95%). Melting point, yield and bacterial activity of II are given in Table 2.

Antibacterial activity: The compounds I and II were tested for antibacterial activities by nutrient agar plate diffusion technique, dimethyl formamide used as solvent and the compounds found to be active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* in various concentrations.

Results and Discussion

The structure of the thiazolidinones were elucidated on the basis of ir spectral data. Schiff bases generally give a strong sharp band at 1630-1615 cm^{-1} (C=N stretch). This band is lost in the formation of thiazolidinones and strong bands at 1750 and 1760 cm^{-1} were characteristic for the carbonyl stretching frequency for thiazolidinone ring system.

It has been observed that in the primary screening of bactericidal activity, the *para* position of phenyl is more potent than *ortho* and *meta*. It has also been observed that introduction of bromine in the phenyl ring increases the activity of 4-thiazolidinones.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi and Bhavnagar University for research scholarships (S.R.S. and S.J.S.) and Dr. S. B. Trivedi, Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre, Amargadh for preliminary antibacterial testing.

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Polyphenolic Constituents of *Rhus mysorensis* leaves

M. SARADA* and D. ADINARAYANA

Department of Chemistry, Sri Venkateswara University,
Tirupati-517 502

Manuscript received 9 November 1982, accepted
25 March 1984

RHUS *mysorensis* (Heyne) (family Anacardiaceae), a thorny shrub distributed in Deccan hill country was not examined earlier for its flavonoid constituents. The present work deals with the chemical examination of *R. mysorensis* leaves. The isolation

* 6-32, S. V. Nagar, Tirupati-517 502.